

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B401
 Date: 17/09/08
 Take Off: 13:33:51Z
 Landing: 17:06:25Z
 Flight Time 3h 32m 34s

Campaign:

Operating Area:

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsey-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Simon Osborne	Met Office	Y
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM	Y
6	Core Chem / CCM2	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	N
7	Cloud Physics	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM	Y
8	Wet Neph / PSAP	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office	
9	CVI	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Met Office	N
10	SWS/SHIMS	Martin Glew	Met Office	Y
11	AMS / SP2	Gavin McMeeking	University of Manchester	N
12	TAFTS	Ralph Beeby	Imperial College	N
13	MARSS / DEIMOS / Mission Scientist 2	Dave Pollard	Met Office	N
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B401
 Date: 18 Sept 2008
 Project: ADIENT
 Location: Bristol Channel, English Channel, E Anglia

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
125443		Start-Up	-.19 kft	263	50'44.15N, 3'25.11W
133111		ASP	-.18 kft	258	Open
133351		T/O	3.9 kft	274	Exeter
133950		JW & Nevz	9.2 kft	275	Zero
134427	135509	Profile 1	10.0 - -.22 kft	274	To 50'
135609	140611	Run 1	0.34 - 0.21 kft	334	Abm WP48, 500'
140612	140841	Profile 2	0.21 - 2.7 kft	338	500-3k'
140842	141841	Run 2	2.7 kft	142	3k', WP49-48
141841	142101	Profile 3	2.7 - 4.7 kft	159	3k-5k'
142101	143045	Run 3	4.7 kft	007	5k' WP48-49
142223		Event	4.7 kft	356	Water on RFC window
143046	143401	Profile 4	4.7 - 1.8 kft	341	2k'
143401	144159	Run 4	1.8 - 1.7 kft	142	WP 49-48, 2k'
144207	144415	Profile 5	1.7 - 0.24 kft	161	500'
144416	144542	Run 5	0.24 - 0.23 kft	359	500'
144542	144657	Orbit 1	0.30 - 0.22 kft	103	50deg left
144732	144845	Orbit 2	0.30 - 0.28 kft	279	50deg, left ,start 270deg
144925	145327	Profile 6	0.32 - 5.0 kft	179	From 500'
145402		Event	5.0 kft	132	Transit 240KIAS
150344	150926	Profile 7	5.0 - 0.25 kft	083	500', WP46
150953	154550	Run 6	0.21 - 0.27 kft	095	500'
152851		Event	0.22 kft	065	QNH 1024
153650		Event	0.24 kft	068	WP 44
154550	154933	Profile 8.1	0.27 - 4.5 kft	089	Sawtooth
154933	155450	Profile 8.2	4.5 - 0.21 kft	088	Sawtooth 1kfpm
155456	163913	Run 7	0.20 - 0.16 kft	054	
155342		Event	0.23 kft	060	WP43
160736		Event	0.24 kft	028	WP 42
161341		Heimann	0.22 kft	015	Cal
162226		Event	0.20 kft	017	WP 41
163747		Event	0.18 kft	322	Abm WP40
163913	164908	Profile 9	0.16 - 10.0 kft	317	1kfpm, 240KIAS
164546		Event	6.8 kft	262	WP 87
170625		Land	0.07 kft	355	Cranfield
170719		ASP	0.07 kft	355	Closed
170959		Shutdown	0.06 kft	307	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W

B401 Track 18-SEP-08

FAAM sortie brief

ADIENT Flight B401

Thursday 18th May, 2008

Other comments:

This flight follows a Caviar flight from Cranfield.

Take off Exeter: 13:00 Z (14:00 L)

Land at Cranfield: 17:00 Z (18:00 L)

Operating Area:

Working over coastal areas Bristol Channel, South (Channel area), and East coasts of Britain

Sortie Objectives:

In-situ sampling of a complex mixture of fresh and aged pollution off the coasts. A mixture of the London plume and continental aerosol is expected in Bristol Channel. Radiation work in the Bristol channel.

Weather

Southeasterly flow in the south is expected to advect continental pollution from London and the continent. Clear skies desired in Bristol Channel area.

Flight patterns:

1. Given clear skies perform pirouette on the runway. (360 degree turn, at around 120 degrees per minute).
2. Take off Exeter at 14:00 local heading north towards Bristol Channel area (AMPEP point 48). [10min, T=10min]
3. Descent profile to arrive at point 48 at 50 ft. [10min, T=20min]
4. Working between points 48 and 49 perform SLRs at different levels above and below pollution layer [40min, T=60min]
5. Perform 2 orbits at low level [5min, T=65min]
6. Fast ascend to 5000 ft or appropriate altitude heading south towards waypoint 46. [25 min, T=90min]
7. Follow route around South coast of England using AMPEP points 46-> 45 -> 44 -> 43 -> 42 -> 41 -> 87 -> 80. Manoeuvres will include sawtooth profiles between 100 and 5000 ft (or top of aerosol layer), with a specific profile around Weybourne. [130min, T=220min]
8. Transit back to Cranfield. [20min, T=240min]
9. Given clear skies and enough light perform pirouette on the runway. (360 degree turn, at around 120 degrees per minute).

Mission Scientist's Debrief Sheet

ADIENT flight B401

18th September 2008

Weather conditions:

Frontal zone lying in the northwest approaches orientated SW to NE, cloud at all levels; frontal cirrus lying through southern Ireland to far north of England. South of this all England and Wales broken Sc and cu which is thicker in the east. Very slack pressure gradient, low winds from the east in the operating area (Bristol Channel and south coast of England). SW approaches in a pressure 'col'. "London plume" forecast to be over the Bristol Channel area and near-continental aerosol expected in the English Channel.

Summary of the flight:

A successful flight was carried out to sample the pollution aerosol plume in the Bristol Channel and along AMPEP points along the south coast as part of the ADIENT project. It is worth noting that the aerosol loadings were moderate during this flight and *lower* than they were north of the Cornish coast during flight B400 that took place several hours earlier. Note also that, except where mentioned below, all the flying below was carried out at an IAS of 210 kts (rather than 200 kts normal science speed) as time was against us for the whole flight and wanted to cover a certain distance in a fixed time period.

The transit from Exeter and profile into the operating area (start point 48) show daytime cumulus over land (tops 6000ft) but clear over the sea. This profile descent showed a strong aerosol increase at 4000ft but relatively light at very low level (500ft) i.e. the plume was somewhat elevated within the marine boundary layer: or perhaps there was a shallow, young MBL that developed below the aerosol layer (old continental BL). This latter scenario makes sense as the tephigram from the profile did not resemble a standard subsidence inversion and well-mixed boundary layer to the surface— there was plenty of structure in there. A series of SLRs was then performed between points 48 and 49 at the following levels:

- (i) **500ft** (pt 48 to pt 49);
aerosol loading drops along run
- (ii) **3000ft** (pt 49 to pt 48);
v. low concs at start, hit the aerosol plume along run; broken cloud above (thin Sc developed over sea at end of run)
- (iii) **5000ft** (pt 48 to pt 49);
above main plume
- (iv) **2000ft** (pt 49 to pt 48);
like the 3000ft run; started clean, then hit aerosol 'bank' almost like a bank of mist/fog; very distinctive to the naked eye; also broken cloud above at end of run

The northern-most edge of the aerosol plume was very marked. Unfortunately, it would seem that the strongest aerosol coincided with broken cloud. A set of 2 orbits was performed at 500ft clear of cloud, 50° angle of bank.

A profile was carried out from 500ft to 5000ft heading to the south of the Devon coast to start routing along the coast. Note the 5000ft transit (IAS 240 kts) was within aerosol over land and also penetrated some cloud (Sc). A profile descent was made into the new area and a run was started at 500ft along the coast eastward to map the aerosol conditions. Initially, pt 46 to pt 45 was not followed as originally planned, but a route closer to the coast to save time. The whole run round to Blakeney (pt 87) near Weybourne saw very little boundary layer cloud. There was a suggestion of more BC in this run from the SP2 instrument compared to the Bristol Channel. The SMPS generally showed two aerosol modes at 30 and 100 nm. Peak NO_x mixing ratios reached 18-25 ppb (probably due to ship plumes in the Dover Straits but not really sure). Aerosol loadings were variable along the track but only moderate (less than $7 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^{-1}$?). One sawtooth was performed between pt 44 and pt 43, between 500ft and 4500ft (the maximum allowed in that area). The top of the profile was not quite above the aerosol, which was a shame, but I estimate that the tops must have been less than 5000ft. Evidence of a double plume in the vertical by eye. The 500ft run was resumed after the sawtooth. AMS indicated mainly sulphate by composition. PCASP steady at around 800/cc in the southeast corner of the route. A profile climb was made towards point 87 (Blakeney), with the important bit of the ascent (i.e. the lower bit that contained the aerosol) taking place east of pt 87. There was a sharp decrease in aerosol at ~2700ft and another weak layer at ~5200ft. There was a good inversion above this. The profile ended over land at FL100.

S. R. Osborne (written 22-09-08).

No SID1
 No SID2
 No CPE
 No CEN(?)

Watch out for POPS noise
 - channel

levels
 4000'
 3000'
 500'

S. L. OSBORNE.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B401**.....

Date **18/09/08**.....

Page **1** of **5**.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1325 z					Vx Exeter:- hazy, No Ci?
1335					Cu: 5/8 cover. Hazy sunshine. To EXETER.
1338		6000' → FL100			BL looks v. polluted, 'white' haze Cu tops → incline.
13426	PI ↓	FL100	274	50°49'N 4°30'W	to Ci in distance (intransit) Start profile descent.
134640		6300'			to Ci above? Cu ends at coast → clear over sea of low cloud over coast?
135010		4300'			→ rotating bit of structure. rise in aerosol? Humidity up a bit.
		4000'			left in turn during descent.
135300		1600'			TOP OF AEROSOL.
		1500'			Good speed in 3 ds of rept.
135426		500'			LABVIEW slings up a No wind rept. fairly well mixed layer so far. vis looks high tho' unclear. Top droplets on rept. (NA classic high)
135506	P1	50'	059		SP2 + AMS report working dr. pressure 108
135610	R1-1	500'	332		End profile descent.
					Start SUR Prompt. 48
140150					SWS looking up.
					Magh signal dropping. POPS 600/a
					SP2 dropping too.
					contacts ahead. Might see them.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.401**.....

Date 18/09/08.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
140430		500'			Rise in aerosol, NOx. Drop in O ₃ ? should be v. little sea salt. No
140610	R1/P2	500'	338	51°18'N 5°0'W	white caps. End SLR, start profile ascent
140850	P2/ R2	3000'	142	51°12'N 5°0'W	(turning in climb) End climb / start run.
		3000'			v. low concn at start of run. can see aerosol layers ahead
141250		3000'			hitting aerosol 'bank'
141622					vis very, very poor here cleared? Sun to our left and above us.
		Peak in 5500'		51°10'N 4°50'W	Sea broken above us - bigger.
141840	R2/P3	3000'		50°47'N 4°36'W	End SLR, profile ascent
142059	P3/ R3	5000'	007	50°48'N 4°47'W	SLR above aerosol (1 cloud).
142404	R3	5000'			Sw's mainly looking down.
143044	R3/R4	5000'	338	51°19'N 5°0'W	Next dropping off - v. low concn.
143400	R4	2000'	142	51°12'N 6°54'W	End SLR, start profile descent. End descent / start SLR at pollutant layer
143800					heading towards plume.
1441					Hit aerosol 'bank'. Under
					under sea again → best aerosol coincides with cloud!
144157	R4/P5	2000'	155	50°48'N 4°36'W	End SLR / start profile descent
144415		500'	357	50°48'N 4°42'W	End profile / start short run to get clear of cloud.

Mission Scientist's Log

IF speed 2 210 knots
from last sortie?

Flight No **B.401**.....

Date 18/09/08.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
144540	01	500'		50°54'N 4°42'W	ORBITS left turn 50° bank below cloud (hope falls) *clear of cloud*
144659	01	500'			End 01
144732	02	500'			Start orbit 2, left turn (50°)
144844	02	500'		50°54' 4°48'	End orbit 2
144926	P6	500'	139	50°54' 4°48'	start profile climbs out of area heading for coast (south) bank into heavier pollution
145039	P6	1950'			End profile ascent - in base of cloud (IAS 240 kts) TRANSIT TO START
145327	P6	5000'	132	50°47' 6°30'	OF "VISURE" PART OF SORTIE v. hazy over land in dense layer at this height - count this as sampling!!
145850	TRANSIT	5000'			Cloud clearing now
1503		5000'			Start profile descent into area tr. cu ahead
150342	P7	500'	083	50°18' 3°42'	Hazy appearance when ASP (0.55 μm) ≈ 45 × 10 ⁻⁶ m ⁻¹
150650		2400'			Start SLR (PSAP pump back on!) clear of cloud. ASP ≈ 65 × 10 ⁻⁶ m ⁻¹
150924		500'	096	50°18' 3°6'	Not actually using AS 46 → 45, were staying closer to the coast instead.
151220		500'			PR → maybe lighter BC content lower different airman to the Bristol channel?

Mission Scientist's Log

ADJENT

Flight No **B.401**..... Date **18/09/08** Name **S.R. Osborne** age **4** of **5**.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
152100		500'			MARSS reporting high altitude moisture? Suggests of this Ci? Cannot see any, but aerosol v. hazy above. Sky not very blue
153250		500'			tile of white to our left
153200		500'	040	50° 30' N 107° 1' W	Nox ~ 18 pct → ship decaying?
153648		500'	071	50° 36' N 054' W	Point 42. 30nm + 100nm → SMPs made
154120		500'			VIS improving?
154549	R6 / P87	500'	090	50° 36' N 0° 6' W	Start profile ascent → saw teeth
	P8.2 ↙	↘ 4500			Can see double plume in the section Top end ascent / descent not quite out of aerosol → very close though!! (Southward) Some structure in neph.
155342	P8.2	1150'	061	50° 36' N 0° 30' E	point 43.
155445	P8.2 P7	500'	055	50° 41' N 0° 30' W	End profile / start sum ^{around} west.
160000		500'			Nox ~ 25 pct!! very high Neph Top variable, SA not particularly high.
160640					Tr. (a) coming up over lead
160735			026	51° 02' N 1° 24' W	Point 42
					A few white caps → 553?
161030					Neph signal v. steady at present Ams / SP2 steady too. Mainly sulphate?

Mission Scientist's Log

IAS = 210 kts

Flight No **B.40.1**.....

Date 18/09/08.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
~1610					ceas? ~80/CC steady for quiet
161820		500'	016	51°56'N 1°42'E	aircraft.
162120					Napl levels dropping gradu. now
162225			015	51°48'N 1°42'E	Shipping near Felixstowe → plumes point 4/ NOx ~6 ppbv bits.
162640			004	52°06'N 1°42'E	↳ blgud ~4 ppbv aerosol bottomed out, small increase now ($27 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$)
163228		500'			vis decreasing again - hazy. Gas increased to $50 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$.
163500					Cloud separation in 315 still.
163740					a few tiny Cu to our right
163912	R7 / P9	500'	317	52°44'N 1°36'E	Abeam point 40 ft End Run & start profile climb. Heading tuds at 87 (Blakeney)
164143	R7	2680' 9			(near Westbourne)
164400		5200'			v. Sharp drop in aerosol to lowest values yet. 2 nd layer → lower conc, but distant.
164532	P9 →	6500'			Contours in distance ahead. left turn at pt - 87
					new cloud now. SCn decd ahead. clear above, Tr. (i) (contours) ahead + to right
164904	P9?	F2100	233	52°48'N 0°36'E	Good inversion End profile ascent + end mission.

IAS
210 kts

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B401 **T/O:** 13:33:51
Date of flight: 18/09/08 **Land:** 17:06:25

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		DONE IN EXETER
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B401
Date of Flight: 18/09/08

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	11213 blocks
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 117033
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 28354 Blocks written = 28354 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y	Start = 133000 End = 171000 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Y Are they non-zero in size? Y
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images 2DC no images 2DP – noise only Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = End = FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	N	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start = 133000 End = 171000</p> <p>Time data processed to =</p> <p>2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	N	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records =</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	N	<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	N	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B401
Date of Flight: 18/09/08

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 0.76
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_proccasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_proccasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proccasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proccasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = b401_tas Y = X+1 = b401_tas_pcasp
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Use flight_plot to check.

B401_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

13:16:41.05 --- - - - -
13:16:41.05 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
13:16:41.06 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
13:16:41.06 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B401
13:16:41.06 --- - - - -
13:17:54.32 SWS - 1000 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 1000ms.
13:17:55.65 SWS - - - 10 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 10ms.
13:17:59.71 SWS - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 200ms.
13:17:59.71 SWS - - - 200 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 200ms.
13:18:04.28 USH - 1000 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 1000ms.
13:18:06.08 USH - - - 10 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 10ms.
13:18:09.23 USH - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 200ms.
13:18:09.24 USH - - - 200 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 200ms.
13:18:11.63 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
13:18:13.33 LSH - - - 10 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 10ms.
13:18:16.00 LSH - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
13:18:16.01 LSH - - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
13:18:22.90 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
13:18:31.57 SWS 0.0 - - - Telescope sent to 90.000
13:18:32.69 SWS 90.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
13:18:43.65 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:18:47.11 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:18:48.77 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:18:51.36 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:19:00.61 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:19:00.62 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:19:00.62 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:19:02.37 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:19:03.86 USH - - - - Idling
13:19:04.10 SWS - - - - Idling
13:19:10.90 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:19:10.90 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:19:11.59 LSH - - - - Idling
13:19:13.34 SWS - - - - Idling
13:19:13.53 USH - - - - Idling
13:19:30.27 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:19:30.28 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:19:30.28 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:19:31.51 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:19:32.93 SWS - - - - Idling
13:19:33.12 USH - - - - Idling
13:19:40.74 LSH - - - - Idling
13:19:41.39 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:19:41.39 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:19:41.41 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:19:58.32 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
13:20:02.94 USH - - - - Idling
13:20:03.09 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:20:04.73 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:20:08.94 USH - - - - Idling
13:25:05.14 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:25:10.24 SWS - - - - Idling
13:25:10.25 USH - - - - Idling
13:25:10.87 LSH - - - - Idling
13:25:11.49 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:25:11.49 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:25:11.51 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:25:11.92 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:25:12.11 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:25:13.12 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:25:13.94 SWS - - - - Idling
13:25:14.14 USH - - - - Idling
13:25:22.35 LSH - - - - Idling
13:25:22.96 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:25:27.41 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:25:27.42 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.

```

13:25:27.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:25:28.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:25:29.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:25:30.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:25:32.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:25:34.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:25:38.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:25:40.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:35:26.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:36:05.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:06.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:06.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:07.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:07.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:07.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:08.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:08.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:08.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:11.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:11.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:11.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:11.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:36:11.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:36:12.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:36:13.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:14.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:17.01	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:36:21.02	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:36:21.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:25.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:25.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:25.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:26.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:36:27.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:28.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:29.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:29.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:31.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:32.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:32.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:32.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:35.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:35.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:35.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:46.24	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:36:47.35	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:36:49.86	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:36:54.74	USH	-	1000	-	-	Sample period changed from 100ms to 1000ms.
13:36:57.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:57.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:57.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:41:39.41	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
13:41:41.61	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
13:42:43.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:44.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:44.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:45.18	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:42:48.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:48.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:48.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:50.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:42:51.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:51.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:52.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:52.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:54.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:54.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:59.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:59.83	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000

13:43:01.51	SWS	170.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:43:02.93	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:43:06.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:06.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:06.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:14.12	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
13:43:17.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:20.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:23.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:23.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:26.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:43:29.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:35.71	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
13:43:35.72	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
13:43:37.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:39.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:40.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:41.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:41.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:51.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:43:52.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:54.33	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
13:43:54.34	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
13:43:55.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:57.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:57.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:59.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:59.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:44:14.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:44:19.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:44:19.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:44:23.10	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
13:44:23.10	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
13:44:24.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:44:25.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:44:26.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:44:49.96	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 176.000
13:44:51.93	SWS	176.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 176.000
13:45:28.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:45:29.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:30.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:32.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:35.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:45:36.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:45:38.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:40.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:41.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:45:50.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:53.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:47:10.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:47:10.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:47:14.33	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
13:47:14.34	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
13:47:15.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:47:18.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:47:19.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:47:21.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:47:22.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:09.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:48:10.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:11.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:14.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:15.71	USH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
13:48:17.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:19.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:19.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:40.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 10 deg C
13:50:11.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:55:16.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

13:55:16.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:55:16.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:55:18.07	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:55:21.65	SWS	176.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:55:23.33	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:55:24.36	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:55:27.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:27.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:27.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:28.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:55:29.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:55:29.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:55:30.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:30.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:32.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:55:33.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:55:37.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:15.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:56:15.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:56:15.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:56:15.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:56:20.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:56:21.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:25.47	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
13:56:25.48	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
13:56:26.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:56:28.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:29.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:53.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:54.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:57.95	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
14:02:57.96	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
14:03:00.46	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
14:03:00.46	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
14:03:01.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:03:04.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:03:06.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:03:07.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:03:20.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:03:23.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:03:24.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:03:26.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:03:27.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:03:29.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:03:31.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:03:32.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:03:33.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:03:42.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:03:42.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:06:14.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:06:14.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:06:14.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:06:15.79	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:06:20.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:20.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:20.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:22.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:06:22.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:06:23.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:06:31.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:06:31.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:31.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:31.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:34.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:06:34.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:06:41.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:06:52.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:52.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:52.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

14:06:53.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:06:54.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:06:54.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:07:03.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:07:05.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 10 deg C
14:07:19.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:07:19.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:07:19.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:07:20.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:07:21.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:07:22.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:07:22.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:07:22.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:07:25.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:07:25.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:07:29.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:07:36.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:07:36.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:07:36.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:08:13.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:14.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:14.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:15.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:15.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:15.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:17.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:08:18.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:18.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:19.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:19.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:21.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:21.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:26.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:43.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:08:43.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:08:43.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:44.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:09:45.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:47.54	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:09:49.23	SWS	171.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:09:50.20	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:09:51.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:10:52.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:10:53.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:54.96	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:10:56.67	SWS	-5.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:10:57.54	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:10:58.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:12:02.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:12:03.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:04.86	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:12:06.51	SWS	167.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:12:07.94	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:12:10.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:13:12.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:13:13.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:13:15.51	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:13:17.20	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:13:18.07	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:13:19.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:20.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:14:22.51	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:14:24.22	SWS	172.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:14:25.18	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:14:48.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:49.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:14:50.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:15:32.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:15:33.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

14:15:35.57	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:15:37.23	SWS	-1.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:15:38.26	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:15:39.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:41.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:16:42.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:44.23	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:16:45.92	SWS	171.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:16:46.96	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:16:48.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:17:51.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:17:51.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:17:53.18	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:17:54.86	SWS	-3.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:17:55.84	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:17:56.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:18:24.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:18:35.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:18:42.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:18:42.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:18:43.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:18:46.49	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:18:50.60	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:18:57.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:18:57.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:18:57.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:18:58.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:19:00.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:00.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:01.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:01.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:03.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:04.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:08.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:29.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 9 deg C
14:19:35.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:35.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:35.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:36.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:19:37.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:38.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:38.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:38.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:41.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:41.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:44.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:19:44.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:19:45.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:20:22.09	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:20:23.79	SWS	172.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:20:25.78	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:20:55.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:20:56.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:21:02.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:02.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:02.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:22:15.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:22:16.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:17.48	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:22:19.18	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:22:20.05	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:22:21.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:11.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:23:12.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:23:13.44	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:23:15.14	SWS	171.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:23:16.10	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:23:16.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:23.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!

14:24:24.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:25.58	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:24:27.25	SWS	-1.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:24:28.29	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:24:29.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:52.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:24:53.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:55.43	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:24:57.15	SWS	173.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:24:58.12	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:24:58.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:26:10.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:26:11.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:26:14.09	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:26:15.80	SWS	-4.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:26:16.67	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:26:17.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:26:33.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:26:34.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:26:37.58	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:26:39.29	SWS	172.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:26:40.16	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:26:41.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:27:45.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:27:46.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:27:47.42	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:27:49.11	SWS	-3.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:27:49.98	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:27:50.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:28:07.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:28:08.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:10.09	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:28:11.80	SWS	172.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:28:12.71	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:28:13.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:29:11.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:29:11.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:29:12.98	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:29:14.68	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:29:15.55	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:29:15.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:29:32.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:29:33.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:29:35.56	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:29:37.23	SWS	169.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:29:38.67	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:29:39.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:30:47.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:30:47.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:30:47.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:30:51.58	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:30:56.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:30:56.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:30:56.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:30:57.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:30:58.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:30:58.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:31:02.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:31:02.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:31:05.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:31:05.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:31:06.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:31:35.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:31:35.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:31:35.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:31:37.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:31:38.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:31:38.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:31:46.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

14:32:18.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:32:18.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:32:18.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:32:20.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:32:21.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:32:21.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:32:21.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:32:21.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:32:24.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:32:24.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:32:29.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:32:32.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:32:32.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:32:32.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:32:43.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:32:43.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:32:43.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:33:30.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:30.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:30.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:32.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:32.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:32.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:34.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:33:35.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:35.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:35.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:35.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:38.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:38.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:43.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:34:03.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:34:03.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:34:03.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:06.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:35:07.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:09.86	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:35:11.57	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:35:12.45	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:35:13.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:11.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:36:12.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:36:14.25	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:36:15.96	SWS	172.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:36:16.84	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:36:17.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:18.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:37:19.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:37:20.82	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:37:22.53	SWS	-4.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:37:23.41	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:37:24.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:25.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:38:26.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:38:27.89	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:38:29.60	SWS	172.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:38:30.47	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:38:31.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:39:32.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:39:33.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:34.99	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:39:35.47	SWS	140.3	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:39:37.13	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:39:37.45	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:39:38.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:40:39.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:40:40.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:40:41.94	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:40:43.63	SWS	171.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.

14:40:44.52	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:40:45.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:46.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:41:47.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:41:49.33	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:41:51.03	SWS	-4.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:41:51.92	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:41:52.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:52.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:42:00.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:00.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:01.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:03.01	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:42:07.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:07.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:07.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:08.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:42:09.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:10.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:11.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:11.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:14.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:14.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:17.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:17.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:17.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:19.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:19.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:20.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:20.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:42:20.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:20.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:23.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:23.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:25.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:25.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:27.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:28.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:29.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:37.65	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
14:42:39.32	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
14:42:43.71	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 200ms.
14:42:45.84	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 200ms.
14:42:50.39	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 30ms.
14:42:50.40	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 30ms.
14:42:59.88	SWS	-	-	35	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 35ms.
14:42:59.91	SWS	-	-	-	35	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 35ms.
14:43:02.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:43:03.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:43:06.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:43:13.45	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:43:13.93	SWS	-1.9	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
14:43:15.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:43:17.91	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:43:25.91	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:43:33.89	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:43:41.91	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:43:49.88	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:43:53.12	SWS	-10.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:43:53.57	SWS	-10.4	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
14:43:56.93	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:43:57.94	SWS	-37.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:44:02.78	SWS	-37.3	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:44:04.39	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:44:05.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:44:16.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:44:17.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:44:20.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:44:21.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

14:44:21.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:33.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:34.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:34.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:45:37.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:45:37.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:46.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:47:00.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:47:01.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:47:02.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:47:19.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:47:27.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:48:27.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:48:47.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:47.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:48.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:50.10	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:48:54.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:54.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:54.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:55.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:55.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:48:56.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:57.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:57.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:58.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:59.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:49:00.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:49:00.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:49:01.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:49:02.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:49:03.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:49:03.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:49:04.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:49:14.63	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 35ms to 200ms.
14:49:14.65	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 35ms to 200ms.
14:49:16.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:49:18.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:49:27.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:49:27.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:49:27.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:50:53.37	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
14:50:55.38	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
14:50:58.16	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
14:51:48.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:51:48.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:51:48.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:51:51.21	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:51:56.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:56.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:56.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:57.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:51:58.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:51:58.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:03.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:03.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:05.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:05.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:06.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:14.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:52:14.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:52:14.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:52:44.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:52:47.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:52:48.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:50.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:52.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:55.02	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
14:52:55.03	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.

14:52:57.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:58.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:59.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:53:28.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:28.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:29.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:31.44	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:53:34.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:34.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:34.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:36.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:36.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:53:37.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:41.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:41.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:42.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:43.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:45.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:50.92	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:53:52.93	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:55:42.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 10 deg C
14:56:16.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:56:41.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:56:41.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:02:12.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:02:12.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:02:12.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:02:14.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:02:14.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:02:14.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:02:15.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:02:15.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:02:16.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:02:17.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:02:17.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:02:18.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:02:19.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:02:19.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:02:19.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:02:21.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:02:22.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:02:22.66	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 75ms.
15:02:23.67	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 75ms.
15:02:24.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:02:25.30	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
15:02:25.31	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
15:02:26.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:02:26.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:02:26.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:02:27.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:02:29.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:02:30.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:02:30.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:02:30.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:02:32.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:02:32.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:02:33.06	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
15:02:34.77	SWS	172.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:02:35.83	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
15:02:37.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:02:39.45	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:02:41.16	SWS	-5.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:02:43.23	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:03:30.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:03:30.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:03:30.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:03:46.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:03:46.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:03:46.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

15:06:14.70	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
15:06:16.17	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
15:08:56.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:08:56.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:08:56.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:08:58.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:58.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:58.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:59.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:09:00.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:00.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:01.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:09:01.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:09:03.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:04.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:04.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:09:04.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:09:07.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:07.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:08.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:27.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:09:27.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:09:27.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:10:06.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:10:08.30	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:10:09.74	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:10:11.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:10:34.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 10 deg C
15:11:16.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:11:17.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:11:19.05	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
15:11:19.47	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
15:11:20.37	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:11:21.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:13:40.01	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:13:45.58	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:19:32.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:19:32.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:19:32.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:19:33.67	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:19:37.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:19:37.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:19:37.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:19:38.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:19:39.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:19:40.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:19:40.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:19:40.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:19:42.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:19:43.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:19:43.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:19:43.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:19:45.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:19:46.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:19:48.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:19:48.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:19:48.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:19:48.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:29:51.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:29:51.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:29:51.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:29:55.28	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:30:00.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:30:00.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:30:00.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:30:02.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:30:03.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:30:03.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:30:03.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

15:30:05.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:30:07.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:30:07.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:30:09.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:30:09.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:30:10.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:30:10.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:30:11.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:30:12.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:30:13.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:30:15.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:30:15.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:30:15.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:38:00.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:38:10.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:38:36.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:38:46.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:39:02.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:39:12.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:39:19.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:39:35.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:39:41.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:39:48.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:39:56.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:40:13.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:40:17.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:40:17.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:40:17.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:40:19.12	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:40:23.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:40:23.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:40:23.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:40:24.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:40:25.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:40:25.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:40:26.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:40:27.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:40:28.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:40:28.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:40:30.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:40:31.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:40:31.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:40:31.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:40:33.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:40:34.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:40:34.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:40:35.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:40:35.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:40:35.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:45:41.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:45:41.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:45:41.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:45:41.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:45:42.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:45:47.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:45:47.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:45:47.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:45:48.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:45:49.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:45:50.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:45:57.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:46:07.66	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
15:46:10.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:46:10.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:46:10.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:47:55.02	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
15:47:56.18	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
15:49:36.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:49:37.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

15:49:37.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:49:40.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:40.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:40.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:41.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:49:42.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:49:42.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:49:50.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:49:51.92	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
15:49:53.39	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
15:49:54.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:54.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:54.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:50:20.32	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
15:50:21.81	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
15:51:47.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 9 deg C
15:54:47.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:54:47.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:54:47.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:54:48.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:48.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:48.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:50.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:54:51.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:54:51.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:54:51.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:51.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:54.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:54:54.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:54:54.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:54.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:57.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:54:57.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:54:59.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:00.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:55:00.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:55:00.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:59:42.69	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
15:59:44.17	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
16:05:07.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:05:07.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:05:07.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:05:09.47	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:05:13.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:05:13.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:05:13.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:05:14.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:05:15.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:05:16.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:05:16.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:05:16.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:05:18.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:05:19.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:05:19.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:05:19.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:05:21.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:05:22.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:05:23.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:05:24.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:05:24.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:05:24.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:17:29.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:17:29.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:17:29.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:17:31.54	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:17:35.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:17:35.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:17:35.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:17:36.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.

16:17:37.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:17:38.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:17:38.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:17:38.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:17:40.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:17:41.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:17:41.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:17:41.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:17:43.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:17:44.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:17:44.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:17:44.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:17:45.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:17:46.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:17:47.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:17:47.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:17:47.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:17:47.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:18:31.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 10 deg C
16:27:50.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:27:50.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:27:50.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:27:52.29	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:27:56.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:27:56.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:27:56.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:27:57.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:27:59.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:27:59.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:27:59.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:27:59.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:28:02.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:28:02.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:28:02.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:28:02.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:28:05.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:28:05.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:28:05.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:28:05.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:28:07.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:28:08.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:28:08.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:28:08.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:28:08.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:28:09.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:38:11.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:38:11.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:38:11.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:38:12.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:38:15.07	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:38:18.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:38:18.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:38:18.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:38:19.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:38:21.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:38:21.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:38:21.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:38:21.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:38:24.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:38:24.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:38:25.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:38:25.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:38:28.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:38:28.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:38:29.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:38:29.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:38:29.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:38:29.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:38:31.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.

16:38:32.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:38:32.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:38:38.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:38:38.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:38:40.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:38:47.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:16.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:39:16.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:39:16.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:39:21.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
16:39:22.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:39:24.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:24.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:24.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:26.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:39:27.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:39:27.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:39:29.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:29.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:35.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:39:36.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:56.59	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
16:39:58.87	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
16:40:11.76	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
16:40:12.76	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
16:43:08.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 8 deg C
16:49:11.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:49:11.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:49:11.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:49:13.24	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:49:18.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:49:18.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:49:18.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:49:19.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:49:20.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:49:21.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:49:21.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:49:21.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:49:23.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:49:24.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:49:24.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:49:24.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:49:26.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:49:27.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:49:28.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:49:32.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** endex

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B400**.....

 Date 18/04/2005.....

 Operator's name: D. TIDDEMAN.....

 Page 1 of 2

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
134241	transit	FL100	10.9	18.2	32.4	—	18°	Chiller ON
134404	Probel	↘	11.7	13.5	32.4	A40	16°	
1354								Lab View died - Restarted
135630	Run 1	500ft	15.2	46.7	76.8	A40	39°	
135800	"	"	15.3	49.4	80.0	A5°	39°	
140406	"	"	15.3	47.8	53.7	A40°	15°	
140840	Run 2	3000ft	14.1	32.7	79.1	A15°	39°	
141209	"	"	14.0	31.1	54.1	A40°	23°	
141535	"	"	14.1	40.9	79.8	A45°	38°	
141830	"	"	13.9	38.0	90.6	A40°	45°	
143410	Run 3	2000ft	14.5	26.0	81.2	A15	40°	
144005	"	"	14.5	44.3	57.2	A40°	18°	
145030	Probel		14.4	45.5	85.2	A15°	40°	
1507								Wet Died again!
150450	Run 6	500ft	15.3	50.0	44.4	A40°	12°	
151606	"	"	15.2	46.1	82.9	A45°	40°	
151750	"	"	15.2	46.1	89.7	A15°	45°	
1524								Died and restarted again
153060	"	"	15.2	46.5	83.5	A10°	40°	
153130	"	"	15.2	46.5	50.0	A40°	11°	

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	18/08/08	Flight	B401	log pages	3
Operator(s)	Pollard		Campaign	CAVIAR			
Departure	Exeter		Arrival	Cranfield			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection	Start-up done on B400				X	
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers					X	
Close all MARSS circuit breakers					X	
FERA on				at time	05:30	
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	16.8°C	Ch	16.9°C	Ch18	16.2°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on				at time	05:33	
Initial target temperatures	Hot	288.4	Cold	285.4		
Target heating					X	
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***					X	
Scanning on (LMD box)				at time	05:37	
Scan indication	Monitor >			Visual	X	

Deimos

Deimos Orientation (Nadir or Zenith)					Z	
Close all Deimos circuit breakers					X	
Turn on Deimos CPU					X	
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***					X	
Start Deimos Software				at time	10:40	
Initial target temperatures	Hot	287.5	Cold	286.4		
Target heating					X	
Scan indication	Monitor >			Visual	X	
Weather	Cloud			Precip		
	Surface			Pressure		
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} + 0$		at time	07:19	
Brightness temps 'sensible'					X
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.6	Cold	284.6
	Deimos:	Hot	344.9	Cold	297.0
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B	
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	
	54.4	14.9	54.7	13.2	
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)
	39.17	32.81	40.29	41.43	43.03

Power changeover

Headset on before start				
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.			
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)				
Exit Deimos Software (x)				
POWER CHANGEOVER				
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton			
Restart Deimos Software				
System running again	at time			

Flight #	B401	Date	18/08/08	Operator(s)	Pollard	log page	3	of	3
<i>Time</i>	Run id	Alt/FL	<i>Remarks</i>				Sys		

Data Processing Log		Initials	Date
Flight data copied from MARSS/Deimos PC flash disk to Martian C:\Bxxx\			
Check disc space on flash disk (need >~10 MB free)			
Copy* Martian logged data from to C:\Bxxx\			
Wave processing run and BT files generated			
DQM file generated and uploaded			
NetCDF file generated and uploaded			
C:\Bxxx\ copied to USB drive or CD			
Data processing issues/notes:			

Flight:

B401

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B401

Date: 17/09/08

Instruments

1. 2DP – lots of noise after take-off
2. Wet Neph – Labview froze in first profile, restarted software but kept freezing.
3. Water droplets on AFC window at 1417Z, 3k'. Didn't appear to fly through cloud although cloud around. Water on inside of window?
4. PCASP – noise dropped off around 1520Z
5. CPC – could not get AIM software to run, i.e. would not go past Error messages "The parameter is not correct" and MFC Application Error. Shutdown at 1600Z.
- 6.

CVI -

Neph – no comms with chiller

PSAP -

SWS -

SHIMS -

AMS / SP2 -

Core Chem -

Cloud physics -

FWVS,TAFTS, AVAPS, ARIES, MARSS, DEIMOS – not operated

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

Nil

MPDS

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Issues

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B401:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
AMS / SP2 log	AMS / SP2 operator does not create a log sheet
TAFTS	TAFTS operator does not create a log sheet
CVI	Jeff: no log to be found on instrument laptop - could be misfiled

AMS - not yet fitted

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	08 Sep 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following video recordings in avi format should be available at the BADC :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080918_r0_b401_133453_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080918_r0_b401_143453_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080918_r0_b401_153453_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080918_r0_b401_163453_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080918_r0_b401_133448_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080918_r0_b401_143448_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080918_r0_b401_153448_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080918_r0_b401_163448_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080918_r0_b401_133447_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080918_r0_b401_143447_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080918_r0_b401_153447_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080918_r0_b401_163447_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080918_r0_b401_133451_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080918_r0_b401_143451_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080918_r0_b401_153451_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080918_r0_b401_163451_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.